

Discussion of the groupoid of Proth numbers (OEIS A080075)

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Abstract Here we show that the set of Proth numbers is a groupoid. The binary operation between the elements of the sets is given as a generalized composition.

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A groupoid is a set with a binary operation [1]. Let us consider the set of the Proth numbers and find the binary operator which is rendering the set a groupoid.

The Proth are integers given by:

$$P_{k,n} = k2^n + 1$$

Integers k and n are given so that k is odd and $2^n > k$. Details on the Proth numbers are given in OEIS A080075.

Let us consider $P_{k,m+n} = k2^{m+n} + 1$. This number is given as:

$$P_{k,m+n} = \frac{1}{k} (P_{k,m} P_{k,n} - P_{k,m} - P_{k,n} + 1) + 1$$

$$P_{k,m+n} = \frac{1}{k} ((k2^m + 1)(k2^n + 1) - (k2^m + 1) - (k2^n + 1) + 1) + 1$$

$$P_{k,m+n} = \frac{1}{k} (k^2 2^{m+n} + k2^m + k2^n + 1 - k2^m - 1 - k2^n - 1 + 1) + 1 = k2^{m+n} + 1$$

Let us define the binary operator as:

$$P_{k,m} \oplus P_{k,n} = \frac{1}{k} (P_{k,m} P_{k,n} - P_{k,m} - P_{k,n} + 1) + 1 \quad (*)$$

This is the same approach we used in some previous works (see [2] and references therein), where we discussed the binary operation of Mersenne, Fermat and other integers, in the framework of the generalized algebras [3,4].

Let us consider $k=1$. We obtain the following numbers (Fermat numbers [2]):

$$P_{1,n} = 2^n + 1, \text{ with } n=1,2,3,\dots$$

That is: 3, 5, 9, 17, 33, 65, 129, 257, 513, 1025, and so on. If $k=3$, we have:

$$P_{3,n} = 3 \cdot 2^n + 1, \text{ with } n=2,3,4,\dots$$

This relation is giving: 13, 25, 49, 97, 193, 385, 769, 1537, 3073, Then we have:

$$P_{5,n} = 5 \cdot 2^n + 1, \text{ with } n=3,4,5,\dots; \quad P_{7,n} = 7 \cdot 2^n + 1, \text{ with } n=3,4,5,\dots$$

$$P_{9,n} = 9 \cdot 2^n + 1, \text{ with } n=4,5,6,\dots; \quad P_{11,n} = 11 \cdot 2^n + 1, \text{ with } n=4,5,6,\dots$$

$$P_{13,n} = 13 \cdot 2^n + 1, \text{ with } n=4,5,6,\dots; \quad P_{15,n} = 15 \cdot 2^n + 1, \text{ with } n=4,5,6,\dots$$

$$P_{17,n} = 17 \cdot 2^n + 1, \text{ with } n=5,6,7,\dots; \quad P_{19,n} = 19 \cdot 2^n + 1, \text{ with } n=5,6,7,\dots$$

and so on. For $k=5$, we have: 41, 81, 161, 321, 641, 1281, 2561, 5121,

Let us note that all these sets of numbers are groupoids as well.

Together, all these sets are giving the sequence in <https://oeis.org/A080075/list>

From <https://oeis.org/A080075>, we have that the Proth numbers can be obtained from other sequences, in the two following manners: 1) $a(n) = \text{A116882}(n+1)+1$, obtained by Klaus Brockhaus, Georgi Guninski and M. F. Hasler, Aug 16, 2010, 2) $a(n) = \text{A157892}(n) \cdot 2^{\text{A157893}(n)} + 1$, by M. F. Hasler, Aug 16, 2010.

From the binary operator (*), we can obtain a recurrence formula from the binary operator, in the following manner. Let us use $P_{k,n+1} = k \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1$ and $P_{k,1} = k \cdot 2^1 + 1 = 2k + 1$. We have:

$$P_{k,n+1} = P_{k,n} \oplus P_{k,1} = \frac{1}{k} (P_{k,n} P_{k,1} - P_{k,n} - P_{k,1} + 1) + 1$$

$$P_{k,n+1} = \frac{1}{k} (P_{k,n} (2k+1) - P_{k,n} - (2k+1) + 1) + 1 = \frac{1}{k} (2kP_{k,n} - 2k) + 1 = 2P_{k,n} - 1$$

The binary operation (*) is commutative and associative, so that:

$$(P_{k,m} \oplus P_{k,n}) \oplus P_{k,o} = P_{k,m} \oplus (P_{k,n} \oplus P_{k,o})$$

Let us note that we could repeat the same approach for numbers of the form $T_{k,n} = k \cdot 2^n - 1$, In the case of $k=3$, we have the Thabit numbers [5]. We obtain a groupoid with binary operator:

$$T_{k,m} \oplus T_{k,n} = \frac{1}{k} (T_{k,m} T_{k,n} + T_{k,m} + T_{k,n} + 1) - 1$$

References

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